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ARE PORTOLAN CHARTS AND PORTOLAN MILE GEOMETRICALLY ROOTED IN CLASSICAL ANTIQUITY? A CARTOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF AL-SHIRAZI'S "GREEK MAP" AND THE *PISANE*, *LUCCA*, *AVIGNON*, AND *CORTONA* CHARTS

Tome Marelić

University of Zadar, Department of Geography

ORCID: 0000-0002-8829-7704

tmarelic@unizd.hr

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ORCID: 0000-0002-8829-7704

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ABSTRACT

Some of the earliest-made known portolan charts (*Pisane*, *Cortona*, *Avignon*, and *Lucca* charts) and Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi's schematic (1282) resembling 'a map of the Mediterranean that was drawn by the sages of Greece and the ancient geometers' were cartometrically analysed. The results show that the Mediterranean was drawn nearly identically on the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart* and that the preserved fragment of the *Avignon chart* is somewhat of an intermediate step between the *Pisane–Lucca* model and Pietro Vesconte's model. The coasts of al-Shirazi's schematic fit well with the *Pisane* and *Cortona* charts, whereas its 40×30 grid is similar in size to the grid drawn on the *Pisane* and *Avignon* charts. The length of its sides along the latitude $\varphi=36^\circ$ (125 km) corresponds to 100 portolan miles (*miglia*) and to a two-degree interval along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ according to Ptolemy's incorrect estimation of the Earth's size. Hypothetically, such a misunderstanding could have occurred if a late medieval cartographer (unfamiliar with the differences between spherical and Euclidean geometry) erroneously combined different spatial datasets from classical antiquity by unwittingly superimposing Ptolemy's longitudes onto maps or charts made according to Eratosthenes's correctly obtained size of the Earth by treating them as distances.

KEYWORDS: portolan charts, portolan mile, *Carte Pisane*, *Cortona chart*, *Avignon chart*, *Lucca chart*, Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi, portolan chart origins, cartometric analysis

INTRODUCTION

If we plotted the known history of cartography on a diagram with the horizontal axis representing the timeline between classical antiquity and the late Middle Ages and the vertical axis representing the planimetric accuracy or the authors' approach to mapmaking, we would see quite dynamic behaviour over time. During classical antiquity, the cartographers adopted an exact approach and invested admirable efforts in devising ways to measure the dimensions of the Earth, determine the position of geographic features as accurately as possible, and plot them on maps. In the third century BCE, Eratosthenes computed the Earth's circumference of 252,000 *stadia* (around 40,000 km),¹ a value that is only slightly less accurate compared to present-day standards (Dicks 1960, Dilke 1985, Russo 2004). It was also a period during which map projections were invented and developed. In the first century CE, Marinus of Tyre presumably invented the equidistant cylindrical projection with a standard parallel $\varphi_0=36^\circ$. The works of Marinus are now lost, or they are not yet discovered, but his contributions to geographic and cartographic knowledge were partially preserved in the *Geographike Hyphegesis* book (commonly known as *Geography*) written by Claudius Ptolemy in the second century CE. Ptolemy derived a large portion of spatial information on more than 8,000 locations (6,300 of which were designated with spherical coordinates) from the works of Marinus, albeit criticizing his approach to a certain degree. He thought that a map of a whole *oikoumene* should be made in a projection on which the convergence of meridians is displayed to reflect the sphericity of the Earth and proposed two map projections whose updated modifications are still in use: the equidistant conic projection ($\varphi_0=36^\circ\text{N}$; the parallel of Rhodes), known as *Ptolemy's first projection (Ptolemy I)* and the pseudoconic projection ($\varphi_0=23.8^\circ\text{N}$; the parallel of Syene), so-called *Ptolemy's second projection (Ptolemy II)*. In addition, Ptolemy's assumed circumference of the Earth was 180,000 *stadia* (29,000 km), a value that is 1.4 times smaller in comparison to Eratosthenes's accurate estimation (Keuning 1955, Snyder 1993, Berggren and Jones 2000) and which may have unintentionally affected the cartography of later eras—a hypothetical scenario proposed by this research and discussed in more detail in the following chapters.

The late antiquity was somewhat a terminus of the exact and mathematical approach to mapmaking, and the large quantities of previously generated cartographic and scientific knowledge were lost. The Christian cartography of Western Europe during the Middle Ages was embodied in *mappae mundi*, relatively simplistically drawn maps made to represent the religious interpretations of the known world (Woodward 1987), whereas contemporary Islamic cartographers, who discovered scholarly sources from classical antiquity in the former Byzantine provinces during the ninth century, conducted a more scientific approach (Tibbets 1998).

The mid- to late-thirteenth century saw the sudden appearance of nautical cartography in the form of portolan charts (Figure 1, Figure 3, Figure 5) that emerged 'out of thin air' whilst completely lacking resemblance to any older known type of map and began to be produced on a relatively regular level in Italian, Catalan, and Arab workshops during several centuries to come. Some of their most prominent features include networks of colour-coded straight lines radiating in standardised angular intervals from one or more centres, linear scale bars calibrated so that one large interval (*spatium*) contains 50 portolan miles (*miglia*), and a lack of a fundamental orientation due to toponyms written perpendicularly to the coastlines (Campbell 1987, Monmonier 2004, Edson 2007). Their most perplexing feature—the exceptionally realistic and remarkably accurate display of coastlines—attracted a lot of scholarly attention and ignited a continuing debate about the sources of their spatial data. The majority of the map historian community, whose interpretations almost exclusively arise from the descriptive approach, sees the portolan charts as a self-evident fact that late medieval sailors had observed vast quantities of bearing- and distance-data during numerous dead-reckoning navigations, thoroughly recorded them into logbooks, and forwarded those datasets to cartographers who used them to draw the charts (Fischer 1886, Kretschmer 1909, Stevenson 1911, Taylor 1951a, 1951b, Pujades 2007, Gaspar 2007, 2008, 2023). Another perspective, which compares the results of cartometric analyses of portolan charts with known historical sources, argues that it is more likely that portolan charts are late medieval reproductions of some earlier-made cartographic content (Wagner 1896/1969, Nicolai 2014, 2024, Marelić 2024a, 2024b).

¹ According to an assumed *stadium* length of 157.5 metres (Russo 2004, 273-277). For more details, see chapter: [Arguments Supporting Classical Antiquity Origins](#).

SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY

Due to their puzzlingly accurate display of coastlines, portolan charts made by Pietro Vesconte (1318) and Gratius Benincasa (1480) became the first cartographic units subjected to the first-ever cartometric analysis. It was performed in the late nineteenth century by Hermann Wagner, who concludes that it is more likely that they are mosaics of copied sub-charts whose origins are pre-medieval (Wagner 1896/1969, 478, 480–483). Apart from the cartometric conducts made by Albert Clos-Arceuduc (1956), Waldo Tobler (1966), and A. John Duken (1988) that are either less sophisticated or made on a small sample of charts, Scott A. Loomer’s doctoral thesis represents the most extensive such effort. He cartometrically analysed 26 portolan charts in comparison to nine map projections and computed that their geometry is most similar to the Mercator projection (Loomer 1987, 144-146, 166-167). In 2014 and 2024, Roel Nicolai performed extensive cartometric analyses and concluded the great likelihood of their pre-medieval origin (Nicolai 2014, 2024), whereas in 2024, Tome Marelić came to the same reasoning by applying a slightly modified methodological approach to a mainly different sample of portolan charts and portolan atlas composites (Marelić 2024a, 2024b). Important methodological aspects of some of these studies will be explained in more depth throughout the text.

Marelić’s article contains cartometric analysis of some of the earliest-made known portolan charts; the anonymous *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart* and the composite of two charts made by Pietro Vesconte in 1311 and 1313. He concludes that all of them are copies of the same cartographic source whose origins are pre-medieval. Moreover, the research shows that they seem to have been composed of subsections whose planimetric accuracy exceeds the accuracy of their Mediterranean and Black Sea areas (as a whole) by a factor of two (Marelić 2024a, 152). The same results were yielded from his subsequent analysis of seven portolan charts and atlas composites produced between the early fourteenth and mid-sixteenth centuries. He proposes the idea that the typical anticlockwise tilt of portolan chart coastlines might be an unintentional result of a process that occurred in the late Middle Ages in which Italian cartographers tried to piece together the cartographic source material that was originally made in classical antiquity (Marelić 2024b, 16-20). Unlike the complete absence of historical records that support the genuine late medieval origin hypothesis (Campbell 1987, 371-373, Gaspar 2023, 2), this hypothetical sequence of events is somewhat supported by three historical records. The oldest source is the writings of the Persian scholar Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi (1282), who provided instructions on how to construct a matrix consisting of 40×30 square cells that represents a crude drawing of a *map of the Mediterranean that was drawn by the sages of Greece (Yūnān) and the ancient geometers* (Savadi and Campbell 2023, 200–207, 226). Other two sources are the short paragraph on the anonymous *Rex Tholomeus* portolan chart (c. 1360) (Ruderman, Clausen, and Allport 2023) and the excerpt from Benedetto Cotrugli’s *De Navigatione Liber* treatise (1464) (Cotrugli 1464/2005, 60v–61r/216–217),² both of which read that a certain Ptolemy (*Tholomeus*, or *Ptholomeo*) measured the world in length and width and made maps according to which nautical (portolan) charts were made. Marelić’s study lacks the cartometric analysis of some other significant early-made portolan charts, such as the anonymous *Lucca chart* and the fragment of the anonymous *Avignon chart* (Table 1), while the geometry of al-Shirazi’s instructional grid deserves to be scrutinised as well. In order to complement the overall insight into geometric features of the earliest known historical records related to nautical cartography, these artefacts were cartometrically analysed in this study and the results were compared with known historical sources and existing research results. As far as is known to the author, no detailed cartometric analysis of these units has been conducted to this day.

All the examined portolan charts and al-Shirazi’s instructional grid were georeferenced to a modern map in Mercator projection with standard latitude $\varphi_0=36^\circ$ via a 4-parameter Helmert similarity transformation (Modenov and Parkhomenko 1965) using a sufficiently redundant number of control (*identical*) points (Table 1). In such a way, the artefacts are scaled and rotated to obtain the *least squares estimation (LSE)* of their residuals (Figure 4), while their original shapes are retained in relative terms and no input information regarding their geometry is modified or lost during the process itself. Since the initial planimetric accuracy results are obtained in comparison to the Euclidean geometry of a map projection in which progressive distortions of distances are structurally embedded, the georeferenced point-datasets need to be de-projected in addition. First, their projected axial displacements (dX , dY) in kilometres are converted into their corresponding angular displacements ($d\lambda$, $d\varphi$) in degrees, after which they are recomputed into corresponding *geodesic* distances on the surface of the WGS84 ellipsoid ($dLON$, $dLAT$ arcs) in kilometres. After such a conversion is made, average *root*

² Benedetto Cotrugli’s *De Navigatione Liber* is the property of Yale University, Beinecke rare book and manuscript library, Call No.: MS 557 (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/catalog/2005406>). The excerpt appears on pages 60v (image ID: 1029839) and 61r (image ID: 1029840).

mean-square errors of their axial displacements in kilometres can be computed (*RMSE dLON*, *RMSE dLAT*), the larger of which represents the overall average estimated planimetric accuracy of the georeferenced dataset (Jenny and Hurni 2011, 403–405, Nicolai 2014, 209–210, Penzkofer 2016, 27–28).³

Table 1. Information regarding the portolan chart sample.

CHART DESCRIPTION:	SIZE [mm]:	APPROX. MAP SCALE:	TERRITORIAL COVERAGE:	CONTROL POINTS:
The anonymous <i>Carte Pisane</i> , mid- to late-thirteenth century, <i>Bibliothèque nationale de France, département Cartes et plans</i> , GE B-1118 (RES)	1063×519	1:4,800,000	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, (partially), Mediterranean Sea, part of the Black Sea (the majority of which is now damaged beyond recognition)	339
The anonymous <i>Cortona chart</i> ; late thirteenth or early fourteenth century, <i>Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona</i> , Port.105	594×475	1:6,250,000	Atlantic coast of W Europe (partially), Central and East Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea (with Sea of Marmara and Sea of Azov)	293
The anonymous <i>Avignon chart</i> (fragment); late thirteenth or early fourteenth century, <i>Archives départementales de Vaucluse</i> , Portulan 01 3E 54 Reg 888bis	270×410	1:6,950,000	Atlantic coast of W Europe (partially), West Mediterranean Sea (partially)	146
The anonymous <i>Lucca chart</i> ; late thirteenth or early fourteenth century, <i>Archivio di Stato Lucca</i> , Cornice 194/I.	600×358	1:7,900,000	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea (partially),	425 (Med & Black Sea: 395)
The composite of Pietro Vesconte's portolan chart (1311) <i>Archivio di Stato di Firenze</i> , CN 01, and the western sheet of Pietro Vesconte's portolan atlas (1313), <i>Bibliothèque nationale de France, département Cartes et plans</i> , CPL GE DD-687 (RES)	1077×483*	1:5,390,000 (N Atlantic alone: 1:7,200,000)	Central and East Mediterranean Sea and Black Sea (1311 chart); Atlantic coasts of W Europe and NW Africa, W Mediterranean Sea (western sheet of 1313 atlas)	549 (Med & Black Sea: 433)

* The X-axis and Y-axis dimensions of a composite (in millimetres) correspond to its size when treated as a single unit.

GEOMETRIC FEATURES OF EARLY-MADE PORTOLAN CHARTS

In comparison to the *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart*, the *Lucca chart* (the lower part of [Figure 1](#)) and the survived fragment of the *Avignon chart* (the upper left quarter of [Figure 3](#)) were discovered and described only recently. The first description of the relatively small-scale *Lucca chart* discovered in 2000 was provided by Philipp Billion (2011). One of its most notable features are the pieces of artwork that depict the personifications of the winds and were partially preserved in the lower left corner of the chart after it had been trimmed. Billion graphically compared partial shapes of its coastlines to their renderings on the *Carte Pisane*, *Cortona chart*, and two Vesconte's charts, and concludes that, while there was an increase in geographical knowledge of the North Atlantic coasts, the dimensions of the Italian peninsula *seem to have posed a greater problem for the earliest chart makers than the details of its outlines* (Billion 2011, 5). He found that its drawing of the Italian peninsula is similar to that on the *Carte Pisane* but more crude in comparison to Vesconte's chart and he assumes that it must have been made before 1311. In 2013, Ramon Pujades published a paper asserting that both the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart* must have been made much later than assumed (perhaps even in the fifteenth century) due to occurrences of toponyms related to cities established after the late thirteenth century (Pujades 2013), but the idea is contrasted by radiocarbon analysis of *Carte Pisane* parchment that dated it between 1170 and 1270 with 95% certainty (Hofmann and others 2016, according to Livieratos and Boutoura 2018, 162).

³ The planimetric accuracy increases with smaller *RMSE* values, and vice versa.

Figure 1. The anonymous *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart* georeferenced to a modern map in the Mercator projection. Chart sources: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, GE B-1118 (RES); *Archivio di Stato Lucca*, Cornice 194/I. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus and others 2017).

Although the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart* show noticeable differences on the aesthetic level—the *Lucca chart* has been coloured more vividly, depicts contemporary social and political content, and lacks a square grid found on the *Carte Pisane* (Figure 1)—the overlap of their georeferenced coastlines (Figure 2) reveals that the majority of the Mediterranean Sea has been drawn nearly identically on both charts despite the 1.2° difference in their *LSE*-computed clockwise rotations.⁴ Apart from noticeable differences in the shape of the North Atlantic area, the largest graphical difference between the two charts is the rendering of the Adriatic Sea, which is tilted -1.0° on the *Carte Pisane*, and -7.7° on the *Lucca chart*. Some smaller differences between the two charts can be found in their renderings of the Alboran and Ligurian Seas, the islands of Corsica, Sardinia, and Cyprus, and the coasts of Campania, southwest Anatolia, the Gulf of Iskenderun, and the African coast of the East Mediterranean (Figure 2).

⁴ The *LSE*-computed clockwise rotations of charts indicate the anticlockwise tilts of their coastlines (in comparison to a modern map to which they were georeferenced).

Figure 2. Noticeable geometric differences between the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart*. The relative rotations of coastlines are colour-coded to indicate which unit exhibits more pronounced deviations in a certain region. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus and others 2017).

The remains of the *Avignon chart* were discovered in 2002 by accident because the chart had been re-utilised as the parchment cover of the sixteenth-century legal register (Mille 2023). The remaining part of the chart is a vertical strip partially encompassing the West Mediterranean Sea and North Atlantic coasts of Europe (Figure 3). The chart is historically important because it contains square grids drawn around its wind rose and an encircled scale bar calibrated in 100 *miglia*—features that are altogether, as far as is known, shared only with the *Carte Pisane* and will be discussed in more detail in the following chapters.

Georeferencing of the *Avignon chart* across its Mediterranean Sea area reveals that the shapes of its coastlines (when treated as a whole) do not resemble any other contemporaneously made portolan chart georeferenced across their *intersect area*, delimited by the reduced and badly damaged present-day coverage of the *Avignon chart* (observe solid and dashed colour-coded vectorized tracings of coastlines in Figure 3). The estimated planimetric accuracy of the *Avignon chart* is 33.6 km, which is a slightly poorer result in comparison to the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart* (29.5 km, and 28.8 km, respectively), but significantly poorer in comparison to a composite of Pietro Vesconte’s charts made in 1311 and 1313 (13.5 km). A more detailed observation shows that the African coasts of the West Mediterranean, the Gulf of Lion, and the Tyrrhenian Sea on the *Avignon chart* are drawn nearly identically to those on Vesconte’s charts, which implies that all of them were copied using the same source material (on a regional basis at least). In contrast, the Alboran Sea has been rendered as tilted anticlockwise, similarly to the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart*, whereas its mainland and insular coastlines of the Balearic Sea have been rotated clockwise considerably more than on any other chart (Figure 3). The North Atlantic coasts on the *Avignon chart* are most similar to those on the *Carte Pisane*, although the Bretagne region and the entire Bay of Biscay have been, in fact, placed more southwards. The Iberian Peninsula has been rendered most realistically on Vesconte’s 1313 chart but made to a significantly smaller scale, whereas on the *Lucca chart*, the coastline between the Cabo de São Vicente and Bayonne has been rendered to an appropriate map scale.⁵

⁵ A better understanding can be obtained by comparing Figure 3 and Figure 8.

Figure 3. Noticeable geometric differences between the survived fragment of the anonymous *Avignon chart* georeferenced to a modern map in the Mercator projection and the overlapping coastal areas on the *Carte Pisane*, *Lucca chart*, and the composite of Pietro Vesconte’s two charts. The relative rotations of coastlines are colour-coded to indicate which unit exhibits more pronounced deviations in a certain region. Chart source: *Archives départementales de Vaucluse*, Portulan 01 3E 54 Reg 888bis. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus and others 2017).

THE GEOMETRY OF AL-SHIRAZI’S SCHEMATIC OF A “GREEK MAP”

Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi’s instructional grid of a “Greek map” (1282) was thoroughly described in Fateme Savadi and Tony Campbell’s recently published article, in which they conclude that al-Shirazi’s attribution of its origins to *Greek (Yūnān) sages and geometers* was inaccurate because its toponyms are similar to those on the Italian portolan charts (Savadi and Campbell 2023). The article is supplemented with an appendix that contains its transcript in English, utilised as source material to assign its locations to appropriate square cells within the 40×30 matrix (that was graphically created in advance) and to properly determine if a certain cell represents whether a land or sea area. After the square cell matrix was created and all the identical points were assigned to its cells, it was georeferenced to a modern map across its Mediterranean and Black Sea areas (Figure 4). Its average estimated planimetric accuracy in comparison to the Mercator projection is 49.6 km, which is not surprising due to its crude appearance. Moreover, since al-Shirazi only provided a cursory description of his

"Greek map" (making it impossible for a reader to pinpoint exactly where each cell's belonging locations should be put), identical points were plotted on the sides and corners of each square, assuming that they better represented the linear nature of the coastlines.

Figure 4. Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi's schematic of a "Greek map" (1282) georeferenced to a modern map in the Mercator projection and the magnitude and orientation of displacement vectors of its residuals. Al-Shirazi's data source: [Savadi and Campbell 2023](#). Basemap shapefile source: [marineregions.org \(Claus and others 2017\)](#).

The geometry of al-Shirazi's schematic, first reconstructed by Youssouf Kamal in 1936, drew the attention of James E. Kelley Jr., who graphically overlaid its image with the coastline of the *Carte Pisane*. He noticed their astonishing resemblance and concluded that the coastline model of the *Carte Pisane* was widely distributed during the late thirteenth century ([Kelley 1979, 19, 21](#)). Savadi and Campbell's paper mentions that discovery and expands the idea by generating square cell matrices derived from the coastline shapes of the *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart* and comparing them graphically to al-Shirazi's matrix ([Savadi and Campbell 2023, 203-204](#)). The authors noticed that al-Shirazi did not mention the rhumb line network in his description and correctly assumed that he was not aware of the anticlockwise tilt of its coastlines. In this study, a more advanced quantitative approach was utilised, in which the georeferenced image of al-Shirazi's schematic was superimposed onto the vectorized tracings of the georeferenced images of the *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart* ([Figure 5](#)). Although it fits with the coastlines on both charts well, there is a noticeably better agreement with the *Cortona chart*, especially across the Aegean and Black Seas and the Sea of Azov, whereas the Ligurian and Tyrrhenian Seas on the *Carte Pisane* seem to represent a better fit. However, the entire western half of the *Cortona chart* was drawn as rotated 4° clockwise relative to its eastern half, suggesting that the chart has been made by an individual with less advanced copying skills ([Marelić 2024a, 145, 148, 152](#)). Therefore, it could have been possible that a more accurately made version of the *Cortona chart* coastline model existed (with both halves properly rectified) that would geometrically fit al-Shirazi's instructional grid across the entire Mediterranean and Black Sea areas to an even better degree.

Figure 5. The *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart* georeferenced to a modern map and overlaid by vectorized coastlines of georeferenced Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi's 40×30 square grid (1282). Charts sources: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, GE B-1118 (RES); *Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona*, Port.105. Al-Shirazi's data source: [Savadi and Campbell 2023](#). Basemap shapefile source: [marineregions.org](#) ([Claus and others 2017](#)).

GEOMETRICAL RELATIONS WITH CLASSICAL ANTIQUITY

Apart from the seemingly closely related production dates of the *Carte Pisane*, *Avignon chart*, and al-Shirazi's reference to the “Greek map”, there are more common attributes shared between them than those observable by the naked eye. The most evident shared element is the ‘broken’ square grid falling outside the (hidden) wind-rose circles (see [Figure 1](#) and [Figure 3](#)) that is sometimes interpreted as an auxiliary tool designed and utilised by late medieval cartographers to render the coastlines of portolan charts more easily ([Mille 2023](#)). Whatever their interpretation, these square-grid networks never received sufficient attention from academic literature. A closer examination of their physical dimensions reveals that the lengths of their sides correspond to the total lengths of their (encircled) scale bars, representing the distance of 100 portolan miles (*miglia*). On the *Carte Pisane*, the average length of these elements is 27 mm, whereas on the *Avignon chart* (made to approximately

1.5 times smaller scale, see Table 1), their average length is 18 mm. The lengths of squares' sides within al-Shirazi's matrix cannot be determined with ease because his references to distances are only superficial. He states that the length of the Mediterranean (comprised of 30 square cells) is around 1,600 *parasangs* and that the width of its eastern coast (comprised of 5 square cells) is around 260 *parasangs* (Figure 4) (Savadi and Campbell 2023, 226).

The results demonstrate that, when georeferenced to a modern map in Mercator projection (Figure 6), all three artefacts containing the square grids receive exactly the same LSE-computed clockwise rotation of 9.9° and their cells become mutually similar in size—a discovery that prompts further reasoning on two levels. The first level is derived from their mutually identical anticlockwise tilts, suggesting that all of them were most likely created by using the same cartographic source material. The second level arises from the immense similarity in the lengths of their sides, indicating that they may represent an explicit reflection of some specific historical unit of distance. Upon closely examining and contextualising the entire range of findings derived from the cartometric analysis of al-Shirazi's "Greek map" schematic and those square grids in general, three key findings that suggest its classical antiquity origins become apparent.

Figure 6. Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi's schematic of a "Greek map" (1282) georeferenced to a modern map in the Mercator projection and overlaid by vectorized coastlines and square grids of the *Carte Pisane* and *Avignon chart* georeferenced to the same map. Al-Shirazi's data source: Savadi and Campbell 2023. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus and others 2017).

The first finding is that the western border of the georeferenced image of al-Shirazi's schematic passes near the *Canary Islands* (Figure 4). The archipelago, referred to as the *Fortunate Islands* or *The Islands of the Blessed* in ancient times, was considered the furthest western point of the known world (*oikoumene*), and Claudius Ptolemy chose this location to place his prime meridian, ensuring that all other longitudes faced the same (easterly) direction (Berggren and Jones 2000, Martinek and Létal 2023).

The second finding is that squares' side lengths of all three units correspond to a distance of around 125 km along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$, which is important for two reasons. The first one is that the distance of around 1.25 km is the most commonly assumed length of the *miglio*, a unit of distance on portolan charts (Campbell 1987, 389, Freiesleben 1983, 126, Nicolai 2014, 263-264), suggesting that at a specific point in history, the length of one side of squares like these was established as 100 *miglia*. The second reason is that the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ (which passes through Gibraltar and Rhodes) played an important role in the cartography of classical antiquity. Both Marinus and Ptolemy were well aware that the geometry of map projections cannot be completely free of distance-distortions and knew that these distortions could be somewhat controlled by adjusting the parameters of map projections to better fit the cartographic representation of the desired areas. Therefore, they chose $\varphi=36^\circ(\text{N})$, which is about mid-latitude in the Mediterranean, as the standard, true-to-scale parallel for constructing their (either cylindrical or conic) equidistant map projections.

The third finding reveals a somewhat more intricate geometric relationship between squares' side lengths, their quantity, the true size of the Earth, and its perceived size during classical antiquity. It is well known that Ptolemy's assumed circumference of the Earth was 180,000 *stadia* (29,000 km) and that he computed longitudes according to estimated distances between locations. Although he placed his prime meridian far west, his reference meridian, used to compute the longitudes of other locations, was the one that passes through Alexandria (Tupikova 2014, Martínek and Létal 2023). Since Ptolemy's perceived size of the Earth was smaller than its actual size (a value of 252,000 *stadia*, or 40,000 km, that had already been computed by Eratosthenes) by a factor of 1.4, this means that all the distances that had been measured correctly were inaccurately translated into degrees of longitude.⁶ In reality, the length of a one-degree longitudinal arc along the equator is around 111 km, whereas its corresponding value along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ has a length of around 90 km (around 570 *stadia*).⁷ According to Ptolemy's inaccurate estimation in which one-degree longitudinal arc along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ corresponds to 400 *stadia*, the distance-derived longitudinal extent of the Mediterranean Sea becomes (erroneously) comprised of around 60° instead of 42° . The distance of 400 *stadia* (around 63 km) approximates 50 *miglia* on portolan charts, whereas al-Shirazi's distance-division of 30 intervals appears to be Ptolemy's longitudinal division reduced so that one cell represents two degrees (Figure 4), or 100 *miglia*.⁸

If we put al-Shirazi's statements that the Mediterranean Sea is 1,600 *parasangs* long and 260 *parasangs* wide along its eastern coast into the framework of his square grid, it means that each square's side contains around 53 *parasangs*, and that one *parasang* translates to around 2.4 km. However, this cannot be taken for granted because his vertical distance-division, which presumably translates into degrees of latitude, is incorrect. It is because the distance-derived one-degree interval along the great circle (the equator and any meridian with its anti-meridian) of Ptolemy's 'small-sized Earth' translates to 500 *stadia* (around 79 km). Therefore, his latitudinal division of its east coast should have been comprised of 4 intervals instead of 5, and his grid should not have been comprised of squares but of rectangles that are longitudinally compressed by a factor of 0.8, resembling the graticule of Marinus's equidistant cylindrical projection $\varphi_0=36^\circ$.⁹ Since that were not the case, and since the coastline shape of his "Greek map" is far from that on the *plate carrée* projection, whose graticule is made of squares (Figure 7),¹⁰ it is logical to assume that al-Shirazi lacked knowledge regarding the distribution of distances along the longitudinal and latitudinal arcs on the Earth's sphere and how they are distorted depending on the map projection, and that the "Greek map" he saw lacked that information as well.

⁶ For example, if the perceived circumference of the Earth is 40,000 km, a distance of 1,000 km along the equator translates to 9.0° of longitude, whereas the same distance translates to 12.4° of longitude if its circumference is perceived as having 29,000 km in length. In the first scenario, a distance of 1,000 km represents 1/40 of its circumference ($360^\circ/40=9.0^\circ$), while in the second scenario, it represents 1/29 of its circumference ($360^\circ/29=12.4^\circ$).

⁷ Obtained by multiplying the length of one-degree arc along the equator with $\cos 36^\circ=0.809$ (if Earth is approximated as a sphere).

⁸ For a more detailed explanation, see Figure 9.

⁹ This is due to the fact that the circumference of the standard parallel, as determined by its cosine ($\cos 36^\circ=0.809$), is smaller than the circumference of the Earth's great circle. Therefore, the longitudinal scale on such a map becomes compressed by moving towards the equator and stretched by moving towards the poles, with poles drawn as lines equal in length to the equator (regardless of the perceived size of the Earth).

¹⁰ Its estimated planimetric accuracy in comparison to a modern map in the *plate carrée* projection (103.3 km, see Figure 7) is poorer than in comparison to a modern map in the Mercator projection (49.6 km, see Figure 4) by a factor of two.

Figure 7. Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi’s schematic of a “Greek map” (1282) georeferenced to a modern map in the *plate carrée* projection. Al-Shirazi’s data source: Savadi and Campbell 2023. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus and others 2017).

ARGUMENTS SUPPORTING CLASSICAL ANTIQUITY ORIGINS

One of the arguments that is most frequently used to support the medieval origin hypothesis is that the anticlockwise tilt of portolan charts of around -10° corresponds relatively well to the value of easterly magnetic declination during the late medieval period that (unknowingly) affected the compasses of sailors who acquired these bearing-data on the field (Pujades 2007, Gaspar 2023). In contrast, the extensive and detailed cartometric analyses reveal that their map scale and anticlockwise tilt values are variable across the chart field and that they show high geometric resemblance to the Mercator projection, which was, as far as is known, invented in the second half of the sixteenth century and was not well-accepted by sailors at first due to its variable map scale (Loomer 1987, Nicolai 2014, 2024, Marelić 2024a, 2024b). This lastly mentioned characteristic represents a total anachronism that cannot be explained at the current level of knowledge. Loomer, who also applied a 4-parameter Helmert transformation in his study, utilised Fernand Braudel’s historical division of the Mediterranean (Braudel 1972, Loomer 1987, 159) and had only a single paleomagnetic value at his disposal (Tanguy 1970), believes that the ‘loxodromic geometry’ of their sub-parts was a direct consequence of unifying a vast array of contemporary bearing-observations that were obtained with high accuracy. Nicolai’s extensive study demonstrates that the Mercator projection cannot be generated in such a way due to its logarithmic nature and provides historical arguments that the mariner’s compass was not commonly used before the mid-fourteenth century, that distances sailed were only estimated before the seventeenth century, and that the late medieval ships had difficulties maintaining course in suboptimal conditions (Nicolai 2014). In addition, both Nicolai’s (2014, 2024) and Marelić’s (2024a, 2024b) results¹¹ demonstrate that the genuine late medieval origin of portolan charts is an unlikely scenario because cartographers seem to have been unable to piece together charts’ sub-parts accurately enough in terms of their map scale, and that the anticlockwise tilts of their western and eastern sub-parts do not correspond to the longitude-wise distribution of contemporary magnetic declination.¹²

¹¹ Nicolai applied a 6-parameter (2014) and a 5-parameter (2024) affine transformation and came to his sub-chart division statistically by rejecting identical points whose residuals exceeded the natural distribution threshold. Marelić applied a 4-parameter Helmert similarity transformation and rejected none of the identical points, assuming that all of them came from a single input source—the human hand of late medieval cartographer prone to non-systematic errors—considering that the identical points extracted from the freehand-drawn coastlines of portolan charts should not be treated as the same as points that were observed during true geodetic and hydrographic surveys (Marelić 2024a, 2024b).

¹² Nicolai used the CALS7k.2 paleomagnetic model (Korte and Konstable 2005) in his 2014 study. Nicolai’s most recent research (2024)

Nicolai notices that the average anticlockwise tilt of portolan charts fits well with the magnetic declination values of thirteenth-century Liguria and proposes that the Genoese cartographers might have posteriori aligned the entire portolan chart image with contemporary magnetic north. He also asserts that the exact historical origins of pre-medieval source material cannot be accurately pinpointed and refrains from making educated guesses (Nicolai 2014, 414). Marelić, who computed that the planimetric accuracy of portolan charts' cartometrically determined *subsections* (Figure 8)¹³ is approximately twice as great in comparison to their Mediterranean and Black Sea areas (as a whole),¹⁴ also noticed that their *LSE*-computed rotations drop to significantly low levels after they are georeferenced to modern maps that closely approximate *Ptolemy I* and *Ptolemy II* projections centred at the longitude near Gibraltar. Moreover, he demonstrates that the anticlockwise tilts of the meridians around Genoa on those maps closely match the anticlockwise tilt of the portolan chart renderings of that area in comparison to the Mercator projection (which does not display the convergence of the meridians). The hypothesis assumes that late medieval Italian cartographers might have obtained an artefact made in classical antiquity, containing large-scale maps or charts made in a cylindrical projection and a small-scale map made in a conic or pseudoconic projection, and that they attempted to recreate it by rotating the copies of its cylindrical parts (going in the direction from west to east) slightly anticlockwise in order to partially mimic the convergence of the meridians on the orientational map centred at the longitude of Gibraltar (Marelić 2024b, 17-19). According to those findings and the existence of three historical records that refer to their pre-medieval origins (al-Shirazi's "Greek map", the anonymous *Rex Tholomeus* portolan chart, and Benedetto Cotrugli's *De Navigatione* book), he proposed a hypothesis that the origin of their source material could be traced to classical antiquity (see chapter: [Scope and Methodology](#)).

This study—in which the results of cartometric analyses were brought into connection with well-documented historical information—provides additional arguments supporting the classical antiquity origins hypothesis, most of which arise from the geometrical and other quantitative features of al-Shirazi's schematic of a map that was, according to his own words, *drawn by the sages of Greece and the ancient geometers*. Although Savadi and Campbell believe that the toponymical content of the text alone can disprove al-Shirazi's assertion, the truth is that it is far simpler to translate toponyms into contemporary linguistic fashion and associate a new set of contemporaneously named locations with an established coastline shape than it is to conduct field observations and plot coastline contours on a 'blank page'. Namely, the original maps from Ptolemy's *Geography*, which are not preserved, seem to have been made by an engineer (*mechanikos*) Agathodaimon from Alexandria, hired as a specialist to convert geographical data into visual frameworks (Mittenhuber 2010, 109), whereas the majority of its classical antiquity annotations posed no difficulty for early modern cartographers to recognise which locations they represented and rename them with success after the book was re-discovered in Western Europe during the Renaissance (Gautier Dalché 2007).

and Marelić's studies (2024a, 2024b) utilised the CALS3k.4 paleomagnetic model (Korte and Konstable 2011).

¹³ For more methodological information regarding how portolan chart *subsections* were determined, see Marelić 2024a.

¹⁴ The same 'rule of thumb' was also discovered by Nicolai in his recent study (Nicolai 2024, 13).

Figure 8. The comparison of the coastlines on the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart* if the Mediterranean Sea area is treated as a whole (black line) and if the charts' coastlines are segmented into cartometrically determined subsections (colour-coded lines). Chart sources: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, GE B-1118 (RES); *Archivio di Stato Lucca*, Cornice 194/I. Basemap shapefile source: *marineregions.org* (Claus and others 2017).

The apparent discrepancy in this hypothesised scenario is the immense longitudinal accuracy of the Mediterranean Sea on portolan charts and al-Shirazi's schematic versus significantly inaccurate longitudes in Ptolemy's data. However, Ptolemy's longitudes were derived from the observed distances, meaning that if we multiply his longitudinal extent of the Mediterranean Sea of 61.8° ¹⁵ by his assumed distance of 400 *stadia* per one degree of longitude along the parallel $\varphi=36^{\circ}$ (Berggren and Jones 2000, 154), we get 24,720 *stadia*, or around 3,900 km—a value that is around 700 *stadia* ($\approx 3\%$) less accurate than the true value of around 3,800 km (around 24,000 *stadia*).¹⁶ This indicates that, despite the inaccuracy of his distance-derived longitudes, the observations of the distances used for those computations appear to be relatively accurate. Some authors believe that Eratosthenes and Ptolemy used the *Attic stadium* of around 185 m (Gulbekian 1987, 43-44). In such a case,

¹⁵ The extent between the *Straits of Herakles* ($\lambda_{\text{Ptol}}=7.5^{\circ}\text{E}$) and *Issos* ($\lambda_{\text{Ptol}}=69.3^{\circ}\text{E}$) (Berggren and Jones 2000, 153).

¹⁶ The extent between Gibraltar ($\lambda\approx 6^{\circ}\text{W}$) and Antioch ($\lambda\approx 36^{\circ}\text{E}$) is 42° , and 42° multiplied by 90 km per degree of longitude along the parallel $\varphi=36^{\circ}$ yields distance of around 3,800 km.

Ptolemy's estimated size of the Earth becomes 33,300 km (instead of 29,000 km), yielding a one-degree arc along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ of around 75 km and a longitudinal extent of the Mediterranean comprised of 51° . Such a value differs from his longitudinal extent by more than 10° , suggesting that he did not use the *Attic stadium* but the smaller one of 157.5 m, reconstructed in 1882 by Friedrich Hultsch in his detailed study of Greek measurements (Russo 2004, 273).

Classical antiquity was a period of prolific scientific effort, whereas Ptolemy's *Geography* is the only known such book that survived late antiquity and the early Middle Ages. Consequently, it would not be implausible that some other equally comprehensive and detailed geographic and cartographic works, which have since been lost or are not discovered yet, and contained longitudes that were estimated with greater accuracy (in accordance with Eratosthenes's measurements of the Earth), have been produced during that period. For instance, Eratosthenes's *Geography* and Hipparchus's *Against the Geography of Eratosthenes*¹⁷ treatises are now lost (Dicks 1960), while the tenth-century Islamic scholar al-Masudi claimed to have studied Marinus's book on geography and concluded that the maps it contained far surpassed those of Ptolemy (Nordenskiöld 1897, 10, Berggren and Jones 2000, 23).¹⁸ Hypothetically, it could have happened that at a certain point in history, two pre-medieval data sources—either in the form of maps or maps accompanied by written information—both of which were made by “ancient geometers” but based on different understandings of the size of the Earth were brought together and submitted to some late medieval cartographer or more talented illustrator to reproduce them. If he were having a collection of large-scale graticule-equipped maps or charts in cylindrical projection made according to Eratosthenes's size of the Earth on the one hand and Ptolemy's information on how distances are translated into longitudinal extents on the other hand, it could have happened that he unwittingly superimposed Ptolemy's inaccurate longitudinal division onto them while trying to integrate them into a unified framework (a portolan chart). In that hypothetical case, a correctly made longitudinal extent of 42 one-degree intervals could have been mistakenly replaced by Ptolemy's inaccurate extent of around 60 one-degree intervals (each comprising around 50 *miglia*) and reduced to a division of 30 equal-distance intervals, later to be referred to as 100 *miglia* (Figure 9). During that time, the dead-reckoning navigation method did not make practical use of graticules, and it is reasonable to assume that late medieval copyist-cartographers would prioritise bearings and consequently replace these square grids with networks of radiating lines entirely.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study, in which the anonymous *Lucca* and *Avignon* charts and al-Shirazi's schematic of a “Greek map” were cartometrically analysed for the first time, yield a set of completely new insights into the earliest known stages of nautical cartography in the Mediterranean region. The Mediterranean appears to have been drawn nearly identically on the *Carte Pisane* and *Lucca chart*, suggesting that the majority of their coverage was copied by using the same template, whereas the preserved fragment of the *Avignon chart* represents an intermediate step between the *Pisane–Lucca* model and Pietro Vesconte's model (1311–13). The average length of squares' sides within grids common to the *Carte Pisane*, *Avignon chart*, and al-Shirazi's schematic is around 125 km along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ —a value that corresponds to 100 portolan miles (*miglia*) and to a two-degree interval along the parallel $\varphi=36^\circ$ according to Ptolemy's incorrect estimation of the Earth's size. Since their coastline shapes are far from those on the *plate carrée* projection, the appearance of these grids suggests that their authors were oblivious to how distances along the longitudinal and latitudinal arcs on the Earth's sphere are distributed and projected. The proposed hypothesis suggests that such a scenario could have occurred if the late medieval cartographer (unfamiliar with differences between spherical and Euclidean geometry) erroneously combined different spatial datasets from classical antiquity by unwittingly superimposing Ptolemy's longitudes onto the manually reproduced mosaic of regional maps or charts that were originally made according to Eratosthenes's correctly obtained size of the Earth by treating them as distances. Although these interpretations pose a paradigm shift from the portolan chart origin theories that are most commonly found in academic literature, they have a strong foundation in terms of exact quantitative results and well-documented historical information. Therefore, they should be approached with an open mind and investigated more broadly in future research.

¹⁷ Hipparchus accepted Eratosthenes's proposed size of the Earth (Dicks 1960, 33).

¹⁸ J. Lennart Berggren and Alexander Jones believe that al-Masudi actually referred to a reconstruction of Ptolemy's text on Marinus.

Eratosthenes's (correctly estimated) size of the Earth of 252,000 stadia
 1° along the parallel $\phi=36^\circ = 570$ stadia (≈ 90 km)

Ptolemy's (incorrectly estimated) size of the Earth of 180,000 stadia

Ptolemy's 1.4 times smaller estimated size of the Earth

Ptolemy's incorrect distance-derived degrees of longitude
 1° along the parallel $\phi=36^\circ = 400$ stadia (≈ 63 km)

latitudes were determined through astronomical methods and remain unaffected by the estimated size of the Earth

Ptolemy's map scaled to match the map with the correct distance-derived longitudes latitude-wise

Map with correct distance-derived longitudes scaled to match Ptolemy's map longitude-wise

Figure 9. The hypothetical scenario about the origin of square grid networks on al-Shirazi's "Greek map" and the anonymous *Carte Pisane* and *Avignon chart*, and the origin of portolan mile (*miglio*). Basemap shapefile source: naturalearthdata.com (accessed May 2024).

REFERENCES:

- Berggren, J.L., Jones, A. 2000. *Ptolemy's Geography: An Annotated Translation of the Theoretical Chapters*. Princeton and Oxford: Princeton University Press.
- Billion, P. 2011. "A Newly Discovered Chart Fragment from the Lucca Archives, Italy." *Imago Mundi* 63(1): 1-33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085694.2011.521326>
- Braudel, F. 1972. *The Mediterranean and the Mediterranean world in the age of Philip II* (trans. Reynolds S). New York: Harper & Row.
- Campbell, Tony 1987. "Portolan Charts from the Late Thirteenth Century to 1500." In *The History of Cartography, Volume 1—Cartography in Prehistoric, Ancient, and Medieval Europe and the Mediterranean*, eds. J.B. Harley, D. Woodward, 371–463. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Claus, S., De Hauwere, N., Vanhoorne, B., Souza Dias, F., Oset García, P., Schepers, L., Hernandez, F. & Mees, J. (Flanders Marine Institute). 2017. Available at <https://www.marineregions.org/>
- Clos-Arceuduc, A. 1956. "L'Énigme des Portulans: Étude sur la Projection et le Mode de Construction des Cartes à Rumbs du XIVe et XVe Siècle." *Bulletin du Comité des Travaux Historiques et Scientifiques: Section de Géographie* 69: 215–231.
- Cotrugli, B. 1464. *O Plovidbi = De Navigatione / Benedikt Kotruljević* (ed. & trans. Salopek D.) 2005. Zagreb: Hrvatska književna baština, posebna izdanja, Ex Libris.
- Dicks, D.R. (ed.) 1960. *The Geographical Fragments of Hipparchus*. University of London classical studies. London: Athlone Press.
- Dilke, O.A.W. 1985. *Greek and Roman Maps*. Ithaca, New York: Cornell University Press.
- Duken, A.J. 1988. "Reconstruction of the Portolan Chart of G. Carignano (c. 1310)." *Imago Mundi* 40(1): 86–95 <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085698808592641>
- Edson, E. 2007 *The world map 1300–1492*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Fischer, T. 1896. *Sammlung mittelalterlicher Welt-und Seekarten italienischen Ursprungs und aus italienischen Bibliotheken und Archiven*. Venezia: Ferdinand Ongania
- Freiesleben, H.C. 1983. "The still undiscovered origin of portolan charts." *Journal of Navigation* 36(1): 124–129. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0373463300028630>
- Gaspar, J.A. 2007. "The myth of the square chart." *e-Perimetron* 2(2): 66–79. ISSN: 1790-3769.
- Gaspar, J.A. 2008. "Dead reckoning and magnetic declination: Unveiling the mystery of portolan charts." *e-Perimetron* 3(4): 191–203. ISSN: 1790-3769
- Gaspar, J.A. 2023. "The Origin of nautical cartography: certitudes, doubts, and perplexities." *International Journal of Cartography*: 1-30: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23729333.2023.2240902>
- Gautier Dalché, Patrick. 2007. "The Reception of Ptolemy's Geography (End of the Fourteenth to Beginning of the Sixteenth Century)". In *The History of Cartography, Volume 3, Part 1 – Cartography in the European Renaissance*, ed. D. Woodward D, 285-364. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Gulbekian, E. 1987. "The origin and value of the stadion unit used by Eratosthenes in the third century B.C." *Archive for History of Exact Sciences* 37: 359-363. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00417008>
- Hofmann, C., Buisson, N., Richardin, P. 2016. "Is the Carta Pisana still the oldest known marine chart? - The results of laboratory analysis and of radiocarbon dating." Oral presentation; book of abstracts, p. 7. *International Workshop on the Origin and Evolution of Portolan Charts*, Lisbon, 6-7 June 2016.

- Jenny, B., Hurni, L. 2011. "Studying Cartographic Heritage: Analysis and Visualization of Geometric Distortions." *Computers & Graphics* 35: 402–411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2011.01.005>
- Kelley, J.E. 1979. "Non-Mediterranean influences that shaped the Atlantic in the early Portolan charts." *Imago Mundi* 31(1): 18-35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085697908592481>
- Keuning, J. 1955. "The history of geographical map projections until 1600." *Imago Mundi* 12(1): 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085695508592085>
- Korte, M., Constable, C. 2005. "Continuous Geomagnetic Field Models for the Past 7 Millennia II: CALS7K." *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems* 6(1): 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004GC000801>
- Korte, M., Constable, C. 2011. "Improving geomagnetic field reconstructions for 0–3 ka." *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors* 188(3–4): 247–259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pepi.2011.06.017>
- Kretschmer, K. 1909. *Die italienischen Portolane des Mittelalters, Ein Beitrag zur Geschichte der Kartographie und Nautik*. Berlin: Veröffentlichen des Instituts für Meereskunde und des geographischen Instituts an der Universität.
- Livieratos, A., Boutoura, C. 2018. "Carte Pisane and its coastline shape," *e-Perimetron* 13(3): 161-181, ISSN: 1790-3769
- Loomer, S.A. 1987. "A Cartometric Analysis of Portolan Charts: a Search for Methodology." PhD diss., University of Wisconsin-Madison.
- Marelić, T. 2024a. "Traces of the Common Origin of Carte Pisane, Cortona Chart and Pietro Vesconte's Charts." *KN - Journal of Cartography and Geographic Information* 74(2): 137-156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42489-023-00154-6>
- Marelić, T. 2024b. "Copying-lineages of portolan chart metrics and implications of their pre-medieval origin." *The international Journal of Cartography*: 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23729333.2024.2349974>
- Martínek, J, Létal, A. 2023. "Astronomically determined localities, the core part of Ptolemy's Geography." *Journal of maps* 19(1): 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2023.2195563>
- Mille, J. 2023. "The Avignon Chart (c. 1300–c. 1310): An Early Attempt to Represent the Northern Regions of Europe on a Nautical Chart." *Imago Mundi* 75(2): 232-243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085694.2023.2273677>
- Mittenhuber, Florian 2010. "The Tradition of Texts and Maps in Ptolemy's *Geography*". In *Ptolemy in Perspective*. Archimedes, vol. 23, ed. A. Jones, 95-119. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Modenov, P.S., Parkhomenko, A.S. 1965. *Geometric Transformations* (trans. M.B.P. Slater). New York, London: Academic Press.
- Monmonier, M. 2004. *Rhumb Lines and Map Wars: A Social History of the Mercator Projection*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Nicolai, R. 2014. "A Critical Review of the Hypothesis of a Medieval Origin for Portolan Charts." PhD diss., Universiteit Utrecht.
- Nicolai, R. 2024. „The origin problem of nautical cartography: the importance of evidence and method." *The international Journal of Cartography*: 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23729333.2024.2352822>
- Nordenskiöld, A.E. 1897. *Periplus: An Essay on the Early History of Charts and Sailing-Directions* (trans. F.A. Bather). Stockholm: P.A. Norstedt & Söner.
- Penzkofer, M. 2016. *Geoinformatics*. Norderstedt: Books on Demand.
- Pujades, R.J. 2007. *Les Cartes Portolanes: la Representació Medieval d'una Mar Solcada*. Barcelona : Institut Cartogràfic de Catalunya.
- Pujades, R.J. 2013. "The Pisana Chart: Really a primitive portolan chart made in the 13th Century?" *Bulletin du Comité Français de Cartographie* (CFC), 216 (6): 17–32.
- Ruderman, B., Clausen, A., Allport, H. 2023. *The Rex Tholomeus portolan chart of 1360*. Barry Lawrence Ruderman Antique Maps Inc., downloadable for free at: <https://www.raremaps.com/gallery/detail/91710/the-rex-tholomeus-portolan-chart-anonymous>

- Russo L. 2004. *The Forgotten Revolution: How Science Was Born in 300 BC and Why it Had to Be Reborn* (trans. S. Levy). Springer Science & Business Media
- Savadi, F., Campbell, T. 2023. "Quṭb al-Dīn al-Shīrāzī's Textual Map of the Mediterranean Sea (1282) and Its Evident Source in a Portolan Chart." *Imago Mundi* 75(2): 199–231. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085694.2023.2275418>
- Snyder, J.P. 1993. *Flattening the Earth: Two Thousand Years of Map Projections*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Stevenson, E.L. 1911. *Portolan Charts: Their Origin and Characteristics with a Descriptive List of Those Belonging to The Hispanic Society of America*. New York: The Knickerbocker Press.
- Tanguy, J.C. 1970. "An Archaeomagnetic Study of Mount Etna: The Magnetic Direction Recorded in Lava Flows Subsequent to the Twelfth Century." *Archaeometry* 12(2): 115-128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.1970.tb00014.x>
- Taylor, E.G.R. 1951a. "The oldest Mediterranean pilot." *Journal of Navigation* 4(1): 81–85. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0373463300048785>
- Taylor, E.G.R. 1951b. "Early charts and the origin of the compass rose." *Journal of Navigation* 4(4): 351–356. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0373463300034214>
- Tibbets, Gerald R. 1998. "The Beginnings of a Cartographic Tradition." In *The History of Cartography, Volume 2, Book 1 - Cartography in the Traditional Islamic and South Asian Societies*, eds. J.B. Harley, D. Woodward, 90-107. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Tobler, W. 1966. "Medieval distortions: the Projections of Ancient Maps." *Annals of the Association of American Cartographers*, 56(2): 351-360. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8306.1966.tb00562.x>
- Tupikova, I. 2014. "Ptolemy's Circumference of the Earth." *Preprint 464*. Max Planck Institute for the History of Science.
- Wagner, H. 1896/1969. "The Origin of the Mediaeval Italian Nautical Charts." *Report of the Sixth International Geographical Congress London*, Royal Geographical Society, 695–705, reprinted in *Acta Cartographica* 5: 476–485.
- Woodward, David. 1987. "Medieval Mappaemundi." In *The History of Cartography, Volume 1 – Cartography in Prehistoric, Ancient and Medieval Europe and the Mediterranean*, eds J.B. Harley, D. Woodward, 286-370. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.